

10.5281/zenodo.7086726

Vol. 05 Issue 09 Sept - 2022

Manuscript ID: #0705

FOCUS CONSTRUCTION IN KOLOKUMA

OKOTORI, EBIKILA BETTY

GENENAL STUDIES UNIT, INTERNATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TOURISM
AND HOSPITALITY, ELEBELE, BAYELSA STATE. 08063302696; ebikilaangese@gmail.com

Corresponding author. *OKOTORI, EBIKILA BETTY
Email: ebikilaangese@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This is a descriptive work that discusses focus construction in the Kolokuma Dialect of the Izon Language. A North Central Ijoid Lect under the Niger-Congo Phylum, spoken in the Kolokuma/Opokuma Local Government Area in Bayelsa State. The objective of this paper is to examine and describe focus construction in Kolokuma with a view to determining how the focus is realised in the language and the constituents that can be focused. Exploiting a native speaker's intuition, data was collected and analysed on Kolokuma through oral interviews. The study shows that focus in Kolokuma is primarily in-situ, that is, it is realised clause internally. The study also shows that the language encodes focus morphologically, using the particles 'ki', 'ko' and 'kiri ki' as focus markers. Some of the constituents that can be focused on in the language are the subject NP, the object NP, the object of the preposition NP, and the verb. The particle 'ko' is used to lay emphasis on locatives (postpositions of location), while 'ki' is used for other prepositions and NPS. 'Kiri ki' is used to focus on short pronouns. The verb is the only constituent that is fronted in the language; it is fronted to a pre-verbal position and a copy is left at the construal site.

KEY WORDS:

Kolokuma, Focus Construction, Constituents and In-situ.

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1.1 Introduction

Focus is a functional element that refers to the part of a sentence that is presented as NEW information (the information that is not already known by the hearer) as opposed to GIVEN (presupposed) information (information that the hearer is already aware of).

Focus can also be seen as that part of a sentence that is made prominent as a result of its contribution of NEW or CONTRASTIVE information; the part that the speaker wants the hearer to take particular note of.

From the foregoing, two things stand out: New Information and Given Information. New Information is the information that the speaker assumes that the hearer does not know. Although the new information may not necessarily be new, what is important is that the speaker codes it in such a way as to draw the hearer's attention to it or to make it emphatic. Given information, on the other hand, is the background knowledge that the hearer has about the subject of discourse. It has been said that given information is the theme or topic of the sentence – what is being talked about while new information (focus) is what is being said about the topic. Jackson (2007, p.74) says focus is what is most newsworthy about the topic.

Focus changes the semantics of a sentence; the same sentence could have two or more meanings or interpretations, depending on the constituent or part that is focused.

The purpose of this paper is to discuss focus constructions in Kolokuma, a dialect of Izon, spoken in the Kolokuma/Opokuma LGA of Bayelsa State. It seeks to identify and describe the various constituents that can be focused in the language, and also examine how focus is realised (encoded) in the language.

2.1 Focus

Focus is a functional element that lays emphasis on a constituent of a sentence. According to Lambrecht (2001, p.10), Focus is the constituent part of a pragmatically structured conversation that is different from previous assumptions. The focused constituent is an unexpected part of the conversation.

Jakendoff (cited in Arokoyo (2009, p.120) posits that Focus signifies the new material in the statement that the speaker suspects the hearer does not know.

Quirk (1973, p.408) observes that Focus is the contrast between information that is known and that which is unknown. That is, the information that is overt and had earlier been furnished by the text and that which was not anticipated.

Matthews (2007, p.142) says, “Focus is an element or part of a sentence given prominence by information or other means. Usually, where there is contrast or emphasis, or a distinction of new Vs given.”

Jackson (2007, p.74) defines focus as “The most newsworthy element in a sentence, usually marked by the nucleus of an intonation unit”.

2.2 Realization of Focus

Focus can be coded or realised in different ways cross linguistically. According to Jones (cited in Arokoyo (2009, p.121), focus is marked “prosodically (English Intonational focus), morphologically (Mandeng) or structurally (English Cleft focus, Yoruba)”.

Examples of Cleft Focus in Owe, a dialect of Yoruba

Subject NP Focus

1(a) Solá rá ìwé

Sola buy book

‘Sola bought a book’

(b) Solá kí o [t:] rá ìwé

Sola FM RP buy book

‘It was Sola that bought a book’

Direct Object NP Focus

2(a) mò ra motò

I buy car

‘I bought a car’

(b) motò; kí mò rá ti

Car FM I buy

‘It is a car that I bought. (Arokoyo, 2009:125-127).

Lambrech (2001, p.20) on the other hand, says focus can be marked through:

- Prosodic shifts (Changes in the unmarked position of focus accents)
- Syntactic shifts (Changes in the unmarked position of focus constituents)
- Cleft formation (biclausal coding of a proposition with concomitant
- Changes in prosody, constituent order and grammatical relation).

He however, acknowledges the fact that focus can be marked morphologically in Japanese, Korean and a great number of African languages. (Bearth1999b) This study is limited to morphological focus.

2.2.1 Morphological Focus

The third way focus is marked in languages is by the use of particles as focus markers. Some languages, like Owe, a dialect of Yoruba, uses a combination of clause initial position and the particle ‘ki’. Some other languages use either focus markers or special positions. Valin (1999, p.5) says Toura, an SOV Mande language that is spoken in Ivory Coast “Presents an elaborated system of focus marking which makes use of both special position as well as focus markers for clause – internal elements’.

3.1 Focus in Kolokuma

Focus in Kolokuma is realised morphologically by using the particles ‘ki’, ‘ko’ and ‘kiri ki’ as focus markers. Kolokuma does not permit the movement or preposing of focused elements to the left periphery of the clause, rather focus in Kolokuma is in-situ. The focus marker occurs clause internally after the constituent that is focused.

3.2 The Constituents of Focus

The constituents of focus that will be discussed in Kolokuma are the subject NP focus, the object NP focus, the object of the preposition focus, the verb focus, the genitive focus, and the personal pronoun focus.

3.2.1 Subject Focus

The focused constituent in subject focus is the subject NP. The focus marker is written immediately after the subject to show that it is the subject that is in focus. The following data exemplifies this:

3(a) Tari fun-bi gou-mi

Tari book-DEF Read-PST

Tari read the book

(b) Tari ki fun-bi gou-mi

Tari FM book-DEF Read-PST

It was Tari that read the book.

4(a) Kala tobou-ma fou gho mu-mi

Small girl-FDEF market LOC go-PST

The small girl went to the market.

(b) Kala toubo-ma ki fou gho mu-mi

Small girl-FDEF FM market LOC go-PST

It was the small girl that went to the market.

3.2.2 Object Focus

In object focus, the verb can subcategorize for one or two arguments, depending on the verb. The verb 'wash' for instance, can subcategorize for one argument; in 'he washed the clothes', clothes is the argument of the verb 'wash'. The verb 'give' on the other hand can subcategorize for two arguments; in she gave me the money, me and money are the arguments of give. Both the direct object and indirect object can be focused in Kolokuma. The focus marker is placed after the constituent that is focused. Examples:

Direct Object

5(a) Tari sili ni I piri-mi

Tari money LINK ISGOBJ give-PST

Tari gave me money.

(b) Tari siliki ni I piri-mi
Tari money FM LINK ISGOBJ give-PST
It was money that Tari gave me

6(a) Ere-ma tobou-ma famu-mi
Woman-FDEF girl-FDEF beat-PST
The woman beat the girl

(b) Ere-ma tobou-ma ki famu-mi
Woman-FDEF girl-FDEF FM beat-PST
It was the girl that the woman beat.

Indirect object

7(a) Tari sili ni I piri-mi
Tari money LINK ISGOBJ give-PST
Tari gave me money.

(b) Sili-bi, Tari I kiri ki piri-mi
Money-DEF Tari ISGSUB FM give-PST
It was me that Tari gave the money

8(a) Ine dau fun fee ni I piri-mi
My father book buy LINK 1SGOBJ give-PST

My father bought a book for me

(b) Fub-bi, ine dau fee ni I kiri ki piri-mi
Book-DEF my father buy LINK 1SGOBJ FM give-PST
It was me my father bought the book for.

3.2.3 Object of Postposition Focus (Preposition)

The object of the postposition can also be focused in Kolokuma. A postposition is a word which shows the relationship between nouns or pronouns in a sentence. The postpositional phrase in Kolokuma is head final. It is called a postposition because it comes after its complement unlike the preposition. In the case of the postpositional focus, the focus marker ‘ki’ changes to ‘ko’ when the postposition is locative but remains ‘ki’ with other forms of postpositions. Examples of post position focus in Kolokuma :

9(a) Tokoni tebulu ogono boo fiyai-bi gbana-mi

Tokoni table top LOC food-DEF placed-PST

Tokoni placed the food on the table.

(b) Tokoni tebulu ogono ko fiyai-bi gbana-mi

Tokoni table top FM food-DEF put-PST

It was on the table that Tokoni put the food.

10(a) Arí fóú ghó mu-yemi

I market LOC go-PROG

I am going to the market

(b) Arí fóú komu-yemi

I market FM go-PROG

It is market that I am going to.

11(a) Erí wo binaówei mo bó-mí

He his brother with come-PST

He came with his brother

(b) Erí wo binaówei mo ki bó-mí

He his brother with FM come-PST

It was with his brother that he came

3.2.4 Verb Focus in Kolokuma

According to Jakendoff (1977:17) in Arokoyo (2009:133), “Only NPS can be focused, i.e., only the constituents that share the feature [-V] can be focused.” Although this is true of the English language, Owe

dialect of Yoruba and some other languages, it is not true of the Kolokuma dialect. The [+V] constituent focus is attested in the language. When a verb is focused, the normal SOV structure of the sentence changes, the object of the sentence is preposed to a clause initial position while the focus phrase is fronted to a pre-verbal position, but a copy of the verb remains at the construal site. This is the only constituent that exhibits fronting in the language.

Examples of verb focus in Kolokuma

12(a) Idisemiobori fe-mi

Idisemi goatbuy-PST

Idisemi bought a goat

(b) Obori-bi, Idisemi fe ki fe-mi (furu-gha)

goat-DEF Idisemi buy FM buy-PST (steal-NEG)

It was buy that shebought the goat (She didn't steal it).

13(a) Tena fun-bi bolei-mi

Tena book-DEF borrow-PST

Tena borrowed the book

(b) Fun-bi, Tena bolei ki bolei-mi, (fe-gha)

Book-DEF, Tena borrow FM borrow-PST (buy-NEG)

It was borrow that Tena borrowed the book, he did not buy it.

14(a) Lade fiyai-bi tangbe-mi

Lade food-DEF throw-PST

Lade threw away the food.

(b) Fiyai-bi, Lade tangbe ki tangbe-mi

Food-DEF, Lade throw FM throw-PST

It was throw that Lade threw away the food.

The verb constituent focus can also be written without an overt subject.

(c) Tangbe ki tangbe-mi, (fii-gha)

Throw FM throw-PST, (eat-NEG)

It is throw that (Lade) threw it, he did not eat it

3.2.5 Genitive Noun Phrase Focus

In genitive NP focus, the whole NP is focused. The focus marker is written after the genitive phrase that is focused, whether it is the subject NP, object NP or object of the preposition NP. Examples of the genitive noun phrase focus in Kolokuma are cited below:

15(a) Ari Tari fun dou-yemi

ISGSUB Tari book find-PROG

I am looking for Tari's book.

(b) Ari Tari fun ki dou-yemi

ISGSUB Tari book FM find-PROG

It is Tari's book that I am looking for.

16(a) Tokoni binaowei sili furu-mi

Tokoni brother money steal-PST

Tokoni's brother stole money

(b) Tokoni binaowei ki sili furu-mi, (ari-gha)

Tokoni brother FM money steal-PST (ISGSUB-NEG)

It is Tokoni's brother that stole money, not me.

3.2.6 Personal Pronoun Focus

Personal pronouns in Kolokuma can receive focus. The personal pronouns change their forms to show case distinctions. For instance, Arí "I", wóni "we", arí "you", áraú "she" etc. are used in the subject position while the short pronouns /i/ "me", /i/ "you", /a/ "her" etc. are used in the object positions. The 'ki' particle is used to focus pronouns used in the subject position while 'kiri ki' is used to focus pronouns used in the object position, except wo "us that uses 'ki'. Examples of the personal pronoun focus in Kolokuma are :

17(a) Ari ine fiyai fii-dou

ISGSUB POSS food eat-PRSPRF

I have eaten my food.

- (b) Ari ki inei fii-dou

ISGSUB FM POSS eat-PRSPRF

It is I that have eaten mine.

- 18(a) Arau sili-bi ni i piri-mi

3SGSUB money-DEF LINK ISGOBJ give-PST

She gave me the money.

- (b) Arau sili-bi ni i kiriki piri-mi

ISGSUB money-DEF LINK ISGOBJ FM give-PST

It was I that she gave the money.

/i/ “me” is glossed as ‘I’ in example (41b) even though it is an object pronoun because it has been focused, but in the (a) counterpart, it is correctly glossed as an object “me”.

4.0 Summary and Conclusion

This study sets out to examine and describe focus constructions in Kolokuma with a view to determining how focus is realised in the language, and the constituents that can be focused. The study shows that focus in Kolokuma is primarily in-situ, though the verb constituent is fronted to a pre-verbal position. The study also shows that the language encodes focus morphologically, using the particles ‘ki’, ‘ko’, and ‘kiriki’ as focus markers. The study showed that ‘ki’ is a productive way of focusing constituents; it is used to focus the subject NP, the object NP, and the verb. The particle ‘ko’ is used to focus the object of the postposition when it is locative, but ‘ki’ for other forms of postpositions, while ‘kiri ki’ is used to focus personal pronouns in object position.

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